

LEGAL FOUNDATIONS FOR MANAGING THE ACTIVITIES OF WOMEN'S AFFAIRS INSPECTORS IN INTERNAL AFFAIRS BODIES

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Abstract: This article analyzes the specific legal framework for managing the activities of women's affairs inspectors in internal affairs bodies. It discusses the ongoing reforms in effectively managing the work of these inspectors. Additionally, it examines the laws regulating the activities of women's affairs inspectors in internal affairs bodies in assisting state organs and institutions.

Keywords: internal affairs bodies, prevention inspectors for women's issues, activities, legal foundations, assistance procedure.

One of the main characteristics of management is the legal regulation of its goals, tasks, and functions. In legal theory, such legal regulation is considered a process of systematic, normative influence aimed at regulating, protecting, and developing social relations in accordance with society's social needs through legal means [16].

Administrative-legal norms reinforce the legal status and functions of the management subject and object, increasing the responsibility of each participant in the society's management system [17].

As a result of reforms carried out in internal affairs bodies over recent years, certain legal foundations have been established for managing the activities of women's affairs inspectors, along with all other structural divisions of the system. These legal foundations - which determine the procedures, forms and methods of activity, powers, main tasks, rights and obligations of women's affairs inspectors in internal affairs bodies, as well as other social and legal relations [18] - comprise the Constitution and laws of the Republic of Uzbekistan, resolutions of the chambers of the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan, decrees, resolutions and orders of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, resolutions of the Cabinet of Ministers, orders and decisions of relevant ministries, state committees and departments, and decisions of local government bodies [16].

Our Constitution legitimized the establishment of a new sovereign democratic state on the world's political map - the Republic of Uzbekistan [19].

All norms and provisions of the Constitution are the primary source of regulation of social relations in a democratic society based on the principles of justice and humanism. In the country, in its administrative-territorial units, JTS and ITS are reflected in a number of provisions of the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan, in particular, in the norms that embody the requirements for the protection of the interests of the citizen, the state, and society from any form of criminal, administrative, and other antisocial encroachments. In particular, as indicated in Article 13 of the Constitution, democracy in the Republic of Uzbekistan is based on universal principles, according to which the highest value is the individual, his life, freedom, honor, dignity, and other inalienable rights. Their provision, along with other state bodies, institutions, and organizations, is the main task of internal affairs

bodies, in particular, inspectors for women's affairs of internal affairs bodies. Article 121 guarantees that public organizations and citizens can assist law enforcement agencies in protecting legality and law and order, the rights and freedoms of citizens. If the basis for organizing cooperation between inspectors of internal affairs bodies on women's issues and the public has been created, then the inadmissibility of interference by state bodies and officials in the activities of public associations, and at the same time, public associations in the activities of state bodies and officials, defines the clear boundaries of this cooperation.

Undoubtedly, the unconditional provision of the principles of the supremacy of the Constitution and law, as well as legality, is an important guarantee of the protection of human rights and freedoms. We need to understand this idea more deeply. From this point of view, strict adherence to the requirements of the Constitution and laws must become the main criterion of our spiritual level and culture[14].

Effective management of the activities of inspectors for women's affairs of internal affairs bodies and increasing the effectiveness of their activities require regular study, analysis, and monitoring of the legal framework in this area, monitoring their compliance with social life. This, in turn, allows for: a) studying and verifying the compliance of subordinate normative legal acts in this area, including departmental acts of the Ministry of Internal Affairs of the Republic of Uzbekistan, with the Constitution and laws; b) monitoring the full implementation of the norms and provisions of our Constitution in laws and subordinate normative legal acts, as well as their application; c) monitoring and studying the interconnection, complexity, and harmony of legal norms in adopted legislative acts; d) studying the extent to which the implementation of laws and subordinate normative legal acts in this area is ensured in practice, is implemented in practice, and benefits society; e) identifying, studying, and taking measures to improve the causes and conditions that lead to the fact that the implementation of some existing laws and subordinate normative legal acts is not ensured and remains only on paper.

Laws regulating the management of the activities of female inspectors of internal affairs bodies: the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On the Prevention of Neglect and Delinquency among Minors" (September 29, 2010) [12], Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On State Youth Policy" (May 14, 2016), September 14) [2]. "On the Protection of Women from Harassment and Violence" [13] (September 2, 2019, No. 3PY-561), Laws regulating the activities of internal affairs bodies' inspectors for women's affairs in assisting state bodies, institutions, and other structural divisions of internal affairs bodies include: the Law "On Operational-Investigative Activities" (December 25, 2012) [3], the Law "On Road Traffic Safety" (April 10, 2013) [4], and the Law "On Fire Safety" (September 30, 2009) [5].

Additionally, in organizing the activities of internal affairs bodies' inspectors for women's affairs, an important role is played by the Laws of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Internal Affairs Bodies" (September 16, 2016) [6], "On Openness of State Authority and Administration Bodies' Activities" (May 5, 2014) [7], "On Appeals of Individuals and Legal Entities" (September 11, 2017) [8], and in organizing cooperation with public structures and citizens, the Laws of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Public Associations in the Republic of Uzbekistan" (February 15, 1991) [9], "On Citizens' Self-Government Bodies" (April 22, 2013) [10], and "On Social Partnership" (September 25, 2014) [11]. It is worth noting that based on the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Internal Affairs Bodies" (September 16, 2016), which is one of the important laws in this field, in 2017 alone, two laws, 22 Presidential

decrees, 30 Cabinet of Ministers resolutions, and numerous other legal documents were adopted to strengthen the legal basis of the Internal Affairs Bodies' activities [15]. Among the adopted legislative acts, there are many that directly regulate the activities of internal affairs bodies' inspectors for women's affairs.

As evident from the above analysis, while there are currently specific laws regulating certain aspects of the activities of internal affairs bodies' inspectors for women's affairs in our country's law enforcement practice, the most important and fundamental area of their activity related to social relations is not regulated within the framework of the law. It should be noted that certain social relations in the sphere of ensuring citizens' safety are to some extent determined by the relevant provisions of the Laws of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Crime Prevention" (May 14, 2014) and "On Internal Affairs Bodies" (September 16, 2016). For example, Article 4 of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Internal Affairs Bodies" includes maintaining public order and ensuring public safety as a direction of activity of the Internal Affairs Bodies.

However, there is no single comprehensive law that directly regulates this area. This leads to fragmentation of legal norms in the legal regulation of social relations within the framework of the activities of internal affairs bodies' inspectors for women's affairs, gaps between subordinate acts, and mutual contradictions. Moreover, the lack of systematization of subordinate regulatory legal acts directly governing the activities to combat women's crime is causing misunderstandings in the application of law during the performance of official duties by subjects in this field.

References:

1. Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Prevention of Offenses" of May 14, 2014 // Collection of Legislative Acts of the Republic of Uzbekistan. - 2017. No. 37. - p. 978.
2. Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On State Youth Policy" of September 14, 2016 // Collection of Legislative Acts of the Republic of Uzbekistan. - 2017. No. 24. - p. 487. <https://lex.uz/mact/449470963>
3. Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Operational Search Activities" of December 25, 2012 // Collection of Legislative Acts of the Republic of Uzbekistan. - 2017. - No. 36. - p. 943.
4. Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Road Traffic Safety" of April 10, 2013 // Collection of Legislative Acts of the Republic of Uzbekistan. - 2015. - No. 52. - p. 645.
5. Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Fire Safety" of September 30, 2009 // Collection of Legislative Acts of the Republic of Uzbekistan. - 2019. - No. 40. - p. 432.
6. Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Internal Affairs Bodies" of September 16, 2016 // Collection of Legislative Acts of the Republic of Uzbekistan. - 2017. - No. 37. - p. 978.
7. Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Openness of Activities of State Authority and Administration Bodies" of May 5, 2014 // Collection of Legislative Acts of the Republic of Uzbekistan. - 2019. - No. 72.
8. Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Appeals of Individuals and Legal Entities" of September 17, 2017 // Collection of Legislative Acts of the Republic of Uzbekistan. - 2017. - No. 37. - p. 977.

9. Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Public Associations in the Republic of Uzbekistan" of February 11, 1991 // Collection of Legislative Acts of the Republic of Uzbekistan. - 2014. - No. 20. - p. 588.
10. Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Citizens' Self-Governance Bodies" of April 22, 2013 // Collection of Legislative Acts of the Republic of Uzbekistan. - 2017. - No. 37. - p. 978.
11. Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Social Partnership" of September 25, 2014 // Collection of Legislative Acts of the Republic of Uzbekistan. - 2017. - No. 37. - p. 978.
12. Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Prevention of Neglect and Juvenile Delinquency" of September 29, 2010 // Collection of Legislative Acts of the Republic of Uzbekistan. - 2017. - No. 37. - p. 978.
13. Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. ZRU-561 "On Protection of Women from Harassment and Violence" dated September 2, 2019 // Electronic source: <https://lex.uz/mact/4494709>.
14. Mirziyoyev Sh.M. The Constitution is a solid foundation for our free and prosperous life, and for further development of our country // Mirziyoyev Sh.M. The consent of our people is the highest assessment of our activities. Vol. 2. - Tashkent: Uzbekistan, 2018. - p. 39.
15. Mukhamedov U.Kh. Reforms in the internal affairs bodies system based on the Action Strategy: results of the first stage and future tasks // Bulletin of the Academy of the Ministry of Internal Affairs of the Republic of Uzbekistan. - 2017. - No. 4. - p. 4.
16. Activities of internal affairs bodies in maintaining public order and ensuring security: Textbook / I. Ismailov, M.Z. Ziyodullayev et al.; Under the general editorship of B.A. Matlyubov. - T.: Academy of the Ministry of Internal Affairs of the Republic of Uzbekistan, 2019. - p. 101.
17. Chetverikov V.S. Administrative Law. Series "Higher Education." Rostov-on-Don: Phoenix, Study Guide. 2004. - p. 14.
18. Administrative Activities of Internal Affairs Bodies: Textbook // I. Ismailov, M. Z. Ziyodullayev et al.; editor-in-chief Sh. T. Ikramov. - T.: Academy of the Ministry of Internal Affairs of the Republic of Uzbekistan, 2014. - p. 121.
19. Odilkoriyev Kh. Constitution and Civil Society. - T., 2002. - p. 7.

